

SPECTRAL CHARACTER OF THE SIMPLE OF ETHERS

Kholmiraev Mekhroj Murodillayevich

Khaydarov Gayrat Shoyimovich

Saitkulov Foziljon Ergashevich

Uzbekistan-Finland Pedagogical Institute, Faculty of Natural and Physical
Culture, Department of Natural Sciences

Tashkent State Agrarian University

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Annotation: In this scientific work, various types of spectroscopy are considered, methods of ionization and ion separation, physico-chemical aspects of mass spectrometric fragmentation processes, the most important areas of fragmentation of the most important classes of organic compounds.

Key words: types of spectroscopy, methods of ionization and ion separation, physico-chemical aspects, fragmentation processes, classes of organic compounds.

Introduction

In this scientific work, various types of spectroscopy are considered, methods of ionization and ion separation, physico-chemical aspects of mass spectrometric fragmentation processes, the most important areas of fragmentation of the most important classes of organic compounds, analytical aspects of mass spectrometry, as well as applications of mass spectrometry are studied. A large section is devoted to mass spectrometry of bioorganic compounds. A separate chapter tells about mass spectrometry without sample preparation. The main attention is paid to approaches for establishing the structure of ethers by mass spectra. This material is supported by a large number of tasks, the solution of which will allow you to gain practical skills in working with spectra[1-10].

Method and results

The characteristic band of ethers in the infrared spectrum is the band at 1150-1080 cm^{-1} corresponding to the vibrations of the C-O-C group.

In the ^1H NMR spectra, the CH_3O group of alkyl ethers has a signal at 3.3-4.0 m.d., and the same group of methylaryl ethers has a signal at 3.7 m. d. The signals of double bond protons in vinyl ethers (of the type $\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{O}$) are at 5.7-7.5 m.d. (α -position) and 3.5-5.0 m. D. (β -position). If we compare these values with the position of the signals in a similar hydrocarbon system $\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{C}$, then the signal of the α -carbon atom is shifted by +1.2 m. d., and the signal of the β -carbon atom is shifted by -1 m. d. In the ^{13}C NMR spectra of saturated ethers, a carbon atom located in the α -position from the oxygen atom gives a signal in the region of 50-100 m.d., and more distant carbon atoms — in the region of 10-60

m. d. In vinyl ethers, double bond carbons ($C=C-O$) give signals at 115-165 m.d. (α -position) and 70-120 m. d. (β -position). At the same time, if we compare the spectra with hydrocarbon systems of type $C = C-C$, then the signal of the α -carbon atom in vinyl ethers is shifted by +15 m. d., and the signal of the β -carbon atom is shifted by -30 m. d. In aromatic esters, the signal of the α -carbon atom of the ring is observed at 135-155 m. d. (a shift of +25 m. d. compared with arene). The signals of the remaining aromatic carbon atoms, when the ether group is introduced, are shifted by -15 m. d. (ortho-position), +1 m. d. (meta-position) and -8 m. d. (para-position).

The experimental part

In the mass spectra of aliphatic esters, the molecular ion appears as a weak signal, for aromatic esters — as an intense signal. The main direction of fragmentation of a molecular ion is the breaking of the bond between α — and β -carbon atoms and the heterolytic breaking of the $C-O$ bond. As a result, ions with a mass (m/z) equal to 31, 45, 59 arise... $M-46$, $M-33$.

Conclusion

For alkylaryl esters, fragmentation proceeds through the loss of the alkyl chain. In diaryl ethers, the molecular ion or the $M-H$ ion loses the CO group, and the bond between the oxygen atom and the aryl substituent also breaks. Also, during mass spectrometry, esters undergo rearrangements with the cleavage of an alcohol molecule or, in the case of aryl esters, with the cleavage of an alkene and the formation of a phenol

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